

TABLE 2—POLAROGRAPHIC CHARACTERISTICS AND $F_j([X])$ FUNCTIONS FOR Pb(II)-NICOTINATE COMPLEXES

C_{∞} (Moles)	i_d (Divs.)	$E_{\frac{1}{2}}$ (-V vs SCE)	$F_0([X])$	$F_1([X])$	$F_2([X])$
0.00	88.25	0.4105	—	—	—
0.05	79.00	0.4235	3.03	40.6	477.4
0.10	75.50	0.4335	6.83	58.3	308.0
0.15	70.50	0.4415	13.52	83.5	443.3
0.20	70.50	0.4465	19.84	94.2	383.5
0.25	70.50	0.4520	30.04	116.2	394.0
0.30	68.25	0.4565	44.15	143.8	421.0
0.35	67.00	0.4600	58.83	165.2	422.0
0.40	64.00	0.4630	77.54	191.3	434.6
0.50	63.00	0.4695	129.70	257.4	479.8

Thus Cd(II) forms three species : $[Cd(Nicotinate)]^+$, $[Cd(Nicotinate)_2]$ and $[Cd(Nicotinate)_3]^-$ with β_1 , β_2 & β_3 to be 20, 40 and 876, whereas Pb(II) forms two complexes species : $[Pb(Nicotinate)]^+$ and $[Pb(Nicotinate)_2]$ with β_1 and β_2 to be equal to 17.5 and 410 respectively. The complexes formed by Pb(II) are stronger than those formed by Cd(II). Polarographic behaviour of α -picolinate complexes with Pb(II) and Cd(II)^{1,2} revealed that α -picolinate forms much stronger complexes than nicotinate.

Alkali-Metal Complexes : Mixed Ligand Complexes of Alkali Metal Salts of Organic Acid with Oxygen and Nitrogen Donor Ligands

A. K. BANERJEE, DHARM PRAKASH,

P. KEJARIWAL & S. K. ROY

Chemistry Department, Patna University, Patna 800 005.

Manuscript received 21 June 1976, revised 20 May 1978, accepted 8 September 1978

References

1. J. J. LINGANE, *Ind. Eng. Chem. Anal. Ed.*, 1943, 15, 583.
2. M. SPALENKA, *Z. Anal. Chem.*, 1943, 49, 126.
3. H. M. HARSHENON, M. E. SMITH and D. N. HUME, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 75, 507.
4. G. SARTORI, *Gazz. Chem. Ital.*, 1934, 64, 3.
5. D. S. JAIN and J. N. GAUR, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1966, 43, 425.
6. D. S. JAIN and J. N. GAUR, *Aust. J. Chem.*, 1965, 18, 1687.
7. D. S. JAIN and J. N. GAUR, *Bull. L. Acad. Polar. Des. Sci.*, 1966, 14, 783.
8. D. S. JAIN and J. N. GAUR, *J. Polarog. Soc.*, 1966, 12, 49.
9. D. S. JAIN, ANAND KUMAR and J. N. GAUR, *J. Polarog. Soc.*, 1967, 13, No. 3.
10. D. S. JAIN, ANAND KUMAR and J. N. GAUR, *J. Polarog. Soc.*, 1968, 14, No. 1.
11. D. DEFORD and D. N. HUME, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, 73, 5320.
12. D. S. JAIN, OM PRAKASH and S. K. BHASIN, *J. Electrochem. Soc. India*, 1976, 25-(3), 139-142.

In our earlier work, we have reported^{1,2} the synthesis of a large number of mixed ligand complexes of the general formula ML_nHL' , with 1-nitroso-2-naphthol as the second ligand, L' .

In order to study the coordinating ability of L' towards alkali metals, in the mixed ligand complex we are now extending this work by synthesising the adducts of alkali metal salts of some organic acids, (L), such as salicylic acid (SalA), 2-hydroxy-3-naphthoic acid (2H3NA), anthranilic acid (AnC), phenyl anthranilic acid (PhAnC), glycine (gly), β -alanine (Aln) etc., with 2-nitroso-1-naphthol (2N1N) (the second ligand L'), in which the nitroso group and the hydroxyl group are in the reverse position.

The derivatives of salicylic acid are of analgesic and therapeutic value. In order to have a comparative study of the donor properties of these acids, their alkali metal complexes have been synthesised with various nitrogen and oxygen containing second ligands.

Experimental

Adducts of alkali metal salts of organic acids with 2-nitroso-1-naphthol and other second ligands :

The general method of preparation consists in adding a slight excess of the second ligand to the concentrated solution of alkali metal salts of the organic acids in the mole ratio of 3:1. The same was then refluxed on a water bath for about half an hour with stirring. The solutions, onkeeping, yield crystalline solid adducts. These crystals were filtered, washed with absolute ethanol and dried in an oven at 80°.

Results and Discussion

All the complexes are stable when stored under dry conditions and have been characterised on the basis of their analytical results and i.r. spectra. The adducts isolated, have the stoichiometry 1:1, except the glycinate and β -alaninate of Rb and Cs, which take up two molecules of 2-nitroso-1-naphthol. All the complexes are also thermally very stable. When heated, they undergo a decomposition at a temperature higher than the melting point of the second ligand. The colours, decomposition temperatures and the analytical results of the complexes are given in Table-1.

TABLE--1 SOME PROPERTIES AND ANALYTICAL DATA.

Compound	Colour	Decoposition (d°C) temperature	Found				Calculated			
			C	H	N	M	C	H	N	M
NaSa1A.2N1N	Yellowish-brown	205	60.4	3.9	3.9	6.8	61.3	3.6	4.2	6.9
KSa1A.2N1N		185	58.6	3.3	3.9	10.8	58.4	3.4	4.0	11.2
CsSa1A.2N1N	Brown (shining needles)	170	46.2	2.9	3.5	29.8	46.1	2.7	3.2	30.0
Na2H3NA.2N1N	Brown	210	65.6	3.5	3.7	5.7	65.8	3.6	3.6	6.0
K2H3NA.2N1N	Yellowish-brown	190	62.4	3.5	3.5	9.3	63.1	3.5	3.5	9.8
Rb2H3NA.2N1N	Brown	180	55.2	3.2	3.2	18.2	56.5	3.1	3.1	19.2
Cs2H3NA.2N1N	Brown	165	52.3	3.0	2.8	26.8	51.1	2.8	2.8	26.9
NaAnc.2N1N	Brown	190	59.6	3.9	8.0	6.6	60.1	3.9	8.4	6.9
KAnc.2N1N	Brown	175	58.8	3.8	7.9	11.2	58.6	3.8	8.0	11.2
CsAnc.2N1N	Brown	162	46.0	3.1	6.4	28.9	46.2	2.9	6.3	29.7
NaPhAnc.2N1N	Brownish-black	185	66.2	4.2	7.1	5.3	67.6	4.1	6.9	5.6
KPhAnc.2N1N	Reddish-brown	178	64.3	4.1	6.6	9.0	65.1	4.0	6.6	9.2
RbPhAnc.2N1N	Grey	166	57.8	3.5	6.0	17.6	58.7	3.6	5.9	18.1
CsPhAnc.2N1N	Reddish-brown	160	54.3	3.2	5.4	24.5	53.3	3.3	5.4	25.7
LiAln.2N1N	Ash	200	57.5	5.0	10.7		58.2	4.9	10.4	—
NaAln.2N1N	Ash	190	53.9	4.5	9.4	7.7	54.9	4.5	9.8	8.1
KAln.2N1N	Brown	172	51.8	4.2	9.0	12.6	52.0	4.3	9.3	13.0
CsAln.2N1N	Brown	165	49.2	3.6	7.6	22.8	48.7	3.5	7.4	23.4
LiGly.2N1N	Grey	210	55.2	4.4	11.4		56.7	4.3	11.0	—
NaGly.2N1N	Grey	190	52.8	4.0	10.4	7.9	53.3	4.0	10.4	8.5
KGly.2N1N	Brown	180	51.2	4.1	9.4	13.2	50.3	3.8	9.8	13.6
RbGly.2N1N	Reddish-brown	170	48.9	3.8		10.9	49.7	3.8		11.2
CsGly.2.2N1N	Reddish-brown	165	45.8	3.4		20.8	46.0	3.5		21.1
K2H3NA.ONP	Light pink	120	54.8	8.7	4.0	10.5	55.8	3.3	3.8	10.7
Na2H3NA.1N2N	Brown-green	172-75	65.4	4.0	3.8	5.8	65.8	3.6	3.6	6.0
K2H3NA.1N2N	"	140-42	62.9	3.9	3.4	9.5	63.1	3.5	3.5	9.8
Rb2H3NA.1N2N	"	135	57.1	3.4	3.2	19.4	56.6	3.1	3.1	19.2
Cs2H3NA.1N2N	"	132	50.7	3.1	3.1	27.6	51.1	2.8	2.8	27.0
Na2H3NA.INAP	Cream	156	62.9	4.3	3.7	6.3	63.5	3.9	3.9	6.4
K2H3NA.INAP	White	150	60.3	4.0	3.9	10.8	60.8	3.7	3.7	10.4
Cs2H3NA.INAP	Cream	136	48.0	3.3	3.2	27.9	48.6	3.0	3.0	28.3
Na2H3NA.8HQ	White	190-94	67.1	4.2	3.7	6.1	67.6	3.9	3.9	6.5
Rh2H3NA.8HQ	Yellow	138-40	57.0	3.6	3.5	20.1	57.5	3.3	3.3	20.4
KAcSa1A.ONP	Pale yellow	222-25	49.4	3.8	3.7	10.6	50.5	3.3	3.9	10.9
LiAcSa1A.1N2N	Brownish-green	140-42	63.3	4.1	3.6	—	63.5	3.9	3.9	—
NaAcSa1A.1N2N	Brown	175	59.5	4.1	3.9	6.2	60.8	3.7	3.7	6.1
KAcSa1A.1N2N	Brown	160-62	57.9	3.9	3.8	9.8	58.3	3.6	3.6	10.6
CsAcSa1A.1N2N	Brown	155-60	46.6	3.3	3.0	26.9	47.3	2.9	2.9	27.4
NaAcSa1A.INAP	White	140-42	57.1	4.2	4.1	6.3	58.1	4.0	4.0	6.5
KAcSa1A.INAP	White	115-18	54.2	4.1	3.7	10.3	55.5	3.8	3.8	10.6
LiAcSa1A.8HQ	Cream	138-40	65.1	4.5	4.1	—	65.2	4.2	4.2	—
NaAcSa1A.8HQ	White	150-53	61.2	4.2	4.3	6.4	62.2	4.0	4.0	6.6
LiBzSa1A.8HQ	White	120-22	69.8	4.3	3.8	—	70.2	4.1	3.5	—
NaBzSa1A.1N2N	Brown	174	65.3	4.1	3.1	5.1	65.9	3.6	3.2	5.3
KBzSa1A.1N2N	Brown	165	62.9	3.8	3.3	8.4	63.5	3.5	3.1	8.6

TABLE 2—SELECTED ABSORPTION BANDS IN DIFFERENT REGIONS (cm⁻¹).

Compound	3500—3000 O—H/O...H...O	2800—2200 O...H...O/O...H...N	2200—1800 O...H...O	1700—1500
2NIN	3280			1654 (N=O)
NaAnc.2NIN		2500	1860	1640 1600
KAnc.2NIN		2510	1900	1640 1610
RbAnc.2NIN		2560	1910br	1650 1600
CsAnc.2NIN		2540	1900	1650 1615
LiGly.2NIN	3100	2720 2600		1625 1595
NaGly.2NIN	3180 3100	2700 2620	2160	1620 1585
KGly.2NIN	3170	2710 2610	2120br	1620sh 1600
RbGly.(2NIN),		2720 2600	2160br	1615 1605
CsGly.(2NIN),	3170	2720 2590	2080	1610sh 1590
LiAln.2NIN	3150		2200	1625 1580
NaAln.2NIN	3200		2190	1620sh 1590
KAln.2NIN	3200		2160br	1620sh 1610
CsAln.(2NIN),	3150		2200	1610 1600
NaSalA.2NIN			1800	1640 1620
KSalA.2NIN			1800	1650 1615
CsSalA.2NIN			1850	1650 1615
Na2H3NA.2NIN			1850br	1610 1590sh
K2H3NA.2NIN			1900	1630 1600
Cs2H3NA.2NIN			1900	1630 1590
<i>o</i> -Nitrophenol	3218			1615 (N=O)
K2H3NA.ONP			1870	1620 1590
KAcSalA.ONP		2200br		1620 1600 br
1-Nitroso-2-naphthol (1N2N)	3300br			1640 (N=O)
Na2H3NA.1N2N			1825	1610 1585
K2H3NA.1N2N			1910	1630 1580
Rb2H3NA.1N2N			1900	1625 1580
Cs2H3NA.1N2N			1800	1630 1585
LiAcSalA.1N2N			1890s	1615sh 1580
NaAcSalA.1N2N			1880	1615 1575
KAcSalA.1N2N			1910	1615 1580
CsAcSalA.1N2N			1910	1615 1585
NaBzSalA.1N2N			1870	1615 1585
KBzSalA.1N2N			1908	1620 1590
Iso-nitrosoaceto-phenone (INAP)	3260			1680 (C=O)
Na2H3NA.INAP		2710	1830	1665 1650
K2H3NA.INAP		2600	1860	1660 1640
Cs2H3NA.INAP		2715	1850	1665 1645
NaSalA.INAP		2640—2600		1660 1640
KAcSalA.INAP				1665 1640
8-Hydroxyquinoline	3440			1580 (C=N)
Na2H3NA.8HQ		2500	1800	1595 1585
Rb2H3NA.8HQ		2220	1800	1590 1580
LiAcSalA.8HQ		2550—2500		1580 1560
NaAcSalA.8HQ		2550—2500		1585 1565

The i.r. spectra of the mixed ligand complexes are given in table 2 and discussed below :

i) The O—H stretching frequency of the second ligand is either absent or shifted down by 100—150 cm⁻¹ with reduced intensity and appear around 2200 cm⁻¹, suggesting a strong hydrogen bonding between O...H . O and N...O...H in the complexes.

ii) The —NH₂ stretching region (3450—3200 cm⁻¹) show a very broad, poorly resolved absorption, typical of strongly hydrogen bonded —NH₂ groups. In anthranilates this absorption is, however, absent.

iii) A new broad band of medium intensity with sub-maxima between 2600 and 2500 cm⁻¹ is seen in

some complexes which is absent in the metal salt or the second ligand.

iv) Another new band of weak to medium intensity is exhibited by most of the complexes around 2200 cm⁻¹. In few cases, this band is exhibited at about 1800 cm⁻¹.

In alkali metal glycinate and β-alanilate complexes, the absorption bands characteristic of the hydrogen bonded >NH⁺ are present.

Besides this, the bands corresponding to the second site of attachment in these ligands, have been found to be shifted down after complexation.

However, none of these complexes showed anomalous broad absorption between $1300-700\text{ cm}^{-1}$, and as such the acid salt structure with very strong $\text{O}\dots\text{H}\dots\text{O}$ is most improbable³.

From our previous¹ and present work with 2N1N, it is observed that donor property of 2N1N is greater than 1N2N towards alkali metal salts. A larger number of alkali metal salts form solid complexes with 2N1N than with 1N2N.

It has been further observed that 2-hydroxy-3-naphthoic acid, which has the same coordinating groups in the same position as salicylic acid and a higher pK value, formed adducts which were found to be stabler than the adducts of alkali metal salicylates, reported earlier.

Similarly acetyl salicylic acid formed relatively smaller number of complexes and with the benzoyl salicylates, only a few compounds were obtained. This may be due to the enhanced solubility of these adducts in absolute ethanol or due to the weak coordinating ability of the ligand. The alkali metal salts of the esters (methyl salicylate and phenyl salicylate) which are more basic did not give any such compound and the second ligands replaced the esters from their alkali metal salts.

References

1. A. K. BANERJEE, A. J. LAYTON, R. S. NYHOLM and M. R. TRUTER, *J. Chem. Soc. (A)*, 1969, 2536; 1970, 292.
2. A. K. BANERJEE, DHARM PRAKASH and S. K. ROY, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1976, 53, 458, 462.
3. D. HADZI, *Pure & Appl. Chem.*, 1965, 11 (3-4), 435-53.

Copper(II) Complexes with Subnormal Magnetic Moments Derived from New Tridentate Schiff Bases

NITYANANDA SAHA*, K. M. DATTA and B. N. MALLICK

Department of Pure Chemistry, University College of Science, Calcutta-700 009.

Manuscript received 5 October 1978, accepted 22 November 1978

TRIDENTATE dibasic Schiff bases are often unique in forcing the metal ions (II and III) to dimerise or polymerise and as a result metal complexes with unusual magnetic and structural properties are formed^{1,2}. This preliminary communication reports the synthesis, magnetic and spectral characteristics of copper(II) complexes with the Schiff bases derived from diacetylmonoxime and salicylhydrazide (Ia) or amino-guanidine (Ib) or cyanoacetylhydrazide (Ic).

Experimental

The Schiff bases were prepared by the reaction of diacetylmonoxime (0.05 mole) and the corresponding

hydrazinoderivative (0.05 mole) in aqueous ethanol. (Addition of equivalent quantity of anhydrous sodium acetate was necessary while using aminoguanidine hydrochloride). The ligands were recrystallised from aqueous alcohol.

Anal : (Ia) : m.p. $259^\circ - 260^\circ$ (d)

(Found : C, 55.70 ; H, 5.20 ; N, 17.60. Calc. for $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{13}\text{O}_3\text{N}_3$:
C, 56.16 ; H, 5.53 ; N, 17.86%)

(Ib) : m.p. $236 - 237^\circ$ (d)

(Found : C, 30.74 ; H, 6.44 ; N, 35.80. Calc. for $\text{C}_8\text{H}_{11}\text{ON}_3\cdot\text{HCl}$:
C, 31.01 ; H, 6.20 ; N, 36.17%)

(Ic) : m.p. 186° (d)

(Found : C, 45.80 ; H, 5.10 ; N, 31.20. Calc. for $\text{C}_7\text{H}_{10}\text{O}_2\text{N}_4$:
C, 46.15 ; H, 5.45 ; N, 30.77%)

General method of synthesis of the complexes :

An aqueous alcoholic solution of the appropriate Schiff base (0.01M) was mixed with a solution of copper(II) chloride dihydrate (0.01M) in the same solvent ; on adding dil.ammonia solution, dropwise to this resulting solution to have a pH around 6-7 the respective complexes precipitated out as coloured (green or brown) microcrystalline varieties. The complex, in each case, was suction filtered, washed with ethanol and dried at room temperature over fused calcium chloride.

Results and Discussion

The results of the elemental analysis (Table I) show that the complexes have 1:1 stoichiometry with the general composition $\text{Cu}(\text{SB})\cdot\text{H}_2\text{O}$ where SBH_2 represents a molecule of any of the three (Ia, Ib or Ic) Schiff bases. The extreme insolubility of these Cu(II) complexes in water and common organic solvents did not permit any determination of molecular weight of these species and at the same time indicated their polymeric nature. The magnetic susceptibilities of the complexes measured by the Gouy method using A.R. $\text{CuSO}_4\cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ as calibrant, show the magnetic moments to lie in the range 0.83-1.34 B.M. (Table I) at room temperature. This value is lower than the spin-only value of 1.73 B.M. required for an $S = \frac{1}{2}$ system. The subnormal magnetic moments observed for these Cu(II) complexes might be attributed to the significant spin exchange between the interacting Cu^{2+} ions.³

These Cu(II) complexes exhibit a characteristic band in the range 550-575 nm which is assigned to a spin-allowed d-d transition ; the other significant band at ~ 390 nm is the subject of much controversy and in a number of complexes it has been recognised as the characteristic band representing the Cu-Cu linkage.^{4,5} However, the high intensity of the 390 nm band in the